

**PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY AND IDEAS OF IBROY ALTINSARI EDUCATIONAL
AND EDUCATIONAL SOURCE**

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Abstract. *Reveal the pedagogical activities and ideas of Ibrai Oltynsarin, his contribution to the foundation of pedagogical science in our country.*

Keywords: *Kazakh teacher, legitimacy, humanism, countries, religious customs.*

Аннотация. *Ибрай Олтынсариннинг педагогик фаолияти ва ҳаяларини, унинг мамлакатимиз педагогика фанининг асосланишига қўйган ҳиссасини очиб бериши.*

Калим сўзлар: *Қозоқ педагоги, окимлик, инсонпарварлик, мамлакатлар, диний одатлар.*

Аннотация. *Раскрыть педагогическую деятельность и идеи Ибрая Олтынсарина, его вклад в основание педагогической науки нашей страны.*

Ключевые слова: *Казахский педагог, правомерность, гуманизм, страны, религиозные обычаи.*

The famous Kazakh pedagogue Ibroy Altinsarin was brought up in the family of the famous Balkoja Bey in Kostanay region, at the age of 9 he entered the seven-year school for Kazakh children in Orinbor, where he received education from the famous oriental researcher V. Grigorev, who served in the border commission. He often goes to his house and reads literature, history, philosophy, etc. and books in scientific fields from his library. Later, the classics of world literature V. Shakespeare, I. Goethe, D. Byron, A. Pushkin, N. Gogol, M. Lermontov, A. Firdavsi, G. Nizami, A. Navoi and others. he studies his works by himself. This situation expands Altinsarin's thinking, increases his desire for science and culture of civilized countries.

He graduated from the school with excellent marks and in 1857-59 his grandfather was the Peseri of Balkoja Bayding, and in 1860 he transferred to the Orinbor Regional Office as a junior translator. Later, he became a teacher at an elementary school in Torgai. From this moment, the educational and pedagogical activity of Altinsarin begins. At that time, it was very difficult to open a school in a remote area: there was a lack of funds, a school house, and educational materials. Moreover, the representatives of regional hokimita and local hokimita looked coldly at such a good deed. But all this could not stop his demand, the figure, satisfied with the idea of enlightenment, enthusiastically set out to realize his goal. He campaigns across the country to raise money to open a school.

On January 8, 1864, the long-awaited school was opened. In 1861, his friend, Kazan University professor N. I. to Ilminsky. In his letter written on January 19, he said: "In January of this year, my long-awaited work came true and the school was opened. There were 14 Kazakh children there, all of them had good hearing... I began to teach the children very enthusiastically, like a hungry wolf attacking a sheep. I try to have a moral influence as much as I can so that they do not become bribe-takers," he says with great joy that he is actively engaged in his favorite work.

I. Oltinsarin taught the children in an interesting, attractive and understandable way. For example, the children who took lessons from the mullahs in the religious schools barely learned the alphabet in a year, while the students who studied under Ibrai learned the alphabet in three

months. The great French pedagogue J. J. Rousseau said: "The source of children's education is work, and education should begin with the work of teaching in the family." considering the history of the development of education in early India, Egypt and Greece: "the desire for knowledge is a characteristic of every human being. People's desire to learn comes from the same need as a person's desire for air," he said.

We can see that the humanitarian approach, which is the golden support of universal education, that is, the principles of being kind to the student, the principles of cooperation between the teacher and the student, is expressed in the pedagogical views of I. Oltinsarin. For example, in his instructions to the heads of two-class schools: "If the children do not understand something, the teacher should not blame them, he should blame himself for not being able to explain to them. When talking to children, one should not get angry, speak politely, be patient, and not use inappropriate expressions, such words will confuse and annoy the students.

He wrote that when evaluating teachers, it is necessary to evaluate them based on their knowledge, and not on their insignificant words. But if you educate them to be naughty, you can destroy the moral qualities of children", and in the story "Fruit Trees" "The value of education is great. "If you don't advise, you will grow like that crooked tree," he said, using the wisdom he gave to his son, and expressed his thoughts on education. Instead of studying Tatar religious customs, Altinsarin pays special attention to teaching children in their native language, raising them on the basis of folk traditions, legends, proverbs, in particular, the materials of folk oral literature, and introduces many examples of bravery, art, and noble moral qualities in young people.

I. Oltinsarin's democratic-educational direction was expressed in three directions of his pedagogical approach. Firstly, he devoted his whole life to opening a school, attracting Kazakh children to study, teaching world scientists and writing educational materials, and secondly, he focused on training teachers of ethics and giving them daily scientific and methodical guidance. Thirdly, in his works, he comprehensively covered the social and political issues of the social life of the Kazakh people of the 19th century. In any of his works, he urged his students to be honest, sincere, hardworking, polite, artistic, civil, avoid bad habits such as theft, violence, lying, drunkenness, and laziness. Realizing that the future of the Kazakh people lies only in art and education, Oltinsarin faced various obstacles in implementing his idea, but he overcame them with perseverance and was able to realize his goal. He opposed the spread of Christianity and the colonial policy of the tsarist government on the basis of the religious education spread by the Tatar mullahs in the Kazakh steppes.

The realization of I. Oltinsarin's goals and interests in the field of enlightenment was greatly benefited by his appointment as a school inspector of Torgay region in 1879 and his tireless work in this position for ten years until the last moments of his life. Even after becoming an inspector, he set about opening schools. He opened Kazakh-Russian two-class schools one after the other in Elek, Nikolaevsk (Kostanay), Torgay, Yrgiz regions, and established a private library next to them. After that, Oltinsarin undertakes to open primary schools and writes "bolystyq Kazakh mektepteri turaly zapiska" to the governor-general. Here, he makes a proposal to open a new type of school, saying that such a school is suitable not only for the Kazakh steppes, but also for the regions of Russia where they migrate all summer and stay in the winter. He also considered the issue of teacher training. According to his suggestion, in 1888, the first teacher's school was opened in Ord. In July 1882, he wrote in a letter to N. I. Ilminsky: "The most necessary thing for public schools is a teacher. "Neither the best pedagogical tool, nor the best state orders, nor the careful

observations of the inspector can equal a teacher," he wrote. If a teacher loves his students from the bottom of his heart, he will not only be devoted to education, but he will be high in the eyes of all parents and people, and he says that "...the ability to predict the future of a child graduating from school depends on the teacher."

Altinsarin is also involved in the development of teachers' skills, as well as the issue of writing educational and methodological tools necessary for them. At his suggestion, K.D. Ushinsky's "Children's World", L.N. Tolstoy's "Alphabet and Study Book", B.F. Bunakov's "Alphabet and Study Tool", Tikhmirov's "Elementary Course of Grammar" were used as manuals in Russian-Kazakh schools. I. Oltinsarin himself wrote two textbooks "Kazakh Chrestomatiya" (1889) for Russian-Kazakh schools on the example of Russian pedagogues and presented them as textbooks for Kazakh-Russian schools. For example, in "Chrestomatiya" he translated valuable examples of oral literature of the Kazakh people, proverbs and poems for children, examples of stories and poems of Russian writers Krylov, Tolstoy, Poulson and others. Y. Oltinsarin said that in the second part of his chrestomaty, he wants to explain natural science, geography, history, chemistry, physics, as well as technical sciences, and thus he intends to collect and exchange knowledge. But his book has not been found yet.

I. Oltinsarin also paid special attention to the problems of teaching methodology. A.A. Mazokhin, F.D. Sokolov, G. In his letters to Balgymbaev and other teachers, he gave a lot of advice on providing children with thorough education, connecting learning with life, and improving teaching methods.

Another meritorious work of I. Oltinsarin in the field of education was to consider the issue of vocational training for Kazakh youth. He paid special attention to this problem and put a lot of effort into opening craft and farming schools. Soon, a craft school was established in Torgai, and before his death he left a will to donate his barn to an agricultural educational institution to be opened in Kostanay. Altinsarin paved the way for the education of Kazakh girls. He opened a boarding school for Kazakh girls in Yrgyz. It was a historical event of great importance in the life of the Kazakh people. He asked the Potsho administration to open girls' schools in all districts of Torgai region. His proposal was fulfilled two years after his death. Such schools were opened in the cities of Torgay, Kostanay, Karabutak, and Aktobe.

I. Oltinsarin was a true patriot who sincerely loved his people and devoted himself to the cultural development of his people.

I. Oltinsarin is a great thinker and public figure of his time. From his bright appearance and actions, we can see a truly noble citizen who dreams of the cultural and economic development of the Kazakh people, the unification of the Kazakh people as a nation, and a mass literate, cultured and educated country. This dream of Ibrai became a Kazakh, and then it was fully realized and won on the Kazakh land.

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